

Visual Analytics of Higher Order Information for Trajectory Datasets

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Abstract : Due to the widespread of mobile sensing, there is a strong need to handle trails of moving objects, trajectories. This paper proposes three visual analytic approaches for higher order information of trajectory data sets based on the higher order Voronoi diagram data structure. Proposed approaches reveal geometrical information, topological, and directional information. Experimental results demonstrate the applicability and usefulness of proposed three approaches.

Keywords : visual analytics, higher order information, trajectory datasets, spatio-temporal data

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